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Gut Microbiota Generated Metabolites of Simvastatin

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Abstract

Introduction: Gut microbiome perturbations and related dysbiosis have been associated with a variety of metabolic diseases and the therapeutic responses of some drugs, including statins. Statins are widely used to retard the atherosclerosis in patients with hyperlipidemia but also have been reported to present anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and immunomodulatory effects. The exact mechanism how gut microflora interact with simvastatin is not clear. Due to emerging role of gut microflora in drug metabolism, the aim of the study was to examine their role in simvastatin metabolism and to identify metabolites formed in that way, since there is no available data yet on this topic in literature.

Materials and methods: After *in vitro* incubation of simvastatin solution (50 ug/mL) with mixture of selected bacteria *Lactobacillus acidophilus* and *Bifidobacterium longum* (10⁸/ml) for twenty four hours, Liquid Chromatography - Tandem Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) with data-dependent scanning was applied for the qualitative and semiquantitative analysis of simvastatin metabolites. Intracellular, extracellular and total content was analysed.

Findings and arguments: After incubation period with probiotic bacteria, concentration of simvastatin itself decreased by 44.1 %. Eight simvastatin metabolites were detected and identified. Metabolites share some of the common fragment ions in MS² spectra with simvastatin (m/z 303, 285, 267, 243, 225, 199, 173) confirming the origin of these compounds. Metabolites were generated by several bacterial enzymatic reactions catalysed by esterases, dehydratases, dehydrogenases, demethylases and hydroxylases. The major metabolite was hydroxylated metabolite of simvastatin hydroxy acid.

Conclusion: Our results suggest that selected bacterial strains are involved in the metabolism of simvastatin. Further *in vivo* studies are needed in order to provide more detailed insight into the pharmacological and toxicological properties of proposed metabolites and to decipher how an alteration in diversity and composition of the gut microbiome in patient with CVD reflects on the production of these metabolites.

Key words: Simvastatin; Gut microbiota; Drug metabolism.

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